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Research Article

**ASSOCIATION BETWEEN SEROPOSITIVITY OF H. PYLORI
INFECTION WITH AVAILABILITY OF UNSTABLE ANGINA**¹Dr Shujaat Abbas, ¹Dr Zunaira Tehreem, ²Dr Hanan Zulfqar¹RHC Haveli Sheikh Raju, Jhang, ²THQ Hospital Chak Jumra Faisalabad.

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Abstract:

Objective: The aim of this research work is to find out the relationship serologic status of the infection of *Helicobacter Pylori* (*H. Pylori*) with the presence of unstable angina (UA).

Methodology: This is an eloquent case-control research work carried out in Allied Hospital Faisalabad. The duration of this research work was from June 2017 to June 2018. The measurement of the levels of serum HP- IgG carried out in the hospital. We drew samples of blood in the duration of this research study from ninety-six patients with an average age of fifty-six years suffering from UA in accordance with the standard of AHA (American Heart Association) & we also collected the samples of blood from ninety-six persons without any heart complication having an average age of fifty-eight years and we stored all these samples at a temperature of 20°C. We studied the results of serology in relation to unstable angina. With the utilization of the Chi square test, calculation of the OR (Odds Ratios) and 95.0% CI (Confidence Intervals) carried out, adjusting for sex, age and recognized factors of risks.

Results: Total 82.30% (n: 79) patients suffering from UA & 61.10% (n: 55) participants in the group of healthy controls appeared as anti-HP-IgG positive. The OR was three with 95.0% confidence interval: 1.90 to 4.30. We found a significant association between the sero-positivity of infection of *H. pylori* and presence of UA. There was no important disparity in gender and age of the participants of both patients and controls groups.

Conclusion: The findings of this study discovered association between occurrences of the infection of *H. pylori* with the presence of UA.

Key Words: *H. Pylori*, Unstable Angina, Association, Sero-Positivity, Temperature.

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INTRODUCTION:

From last few decades, CADs (Coronary Artery Disease) are the serious issue of the health in the whole world with greater than 50.0% mortalities as an outcome of this very complication [1]. There are no known reasons behind atherosclerosis, although there are many described reason are diabetes, history of the family, cigarette smoking, hypertension & hyperlipidemia. But these risk factors are the only 50.0% among risks of coronary artery diseases [1, 2]. More than one hundred years ago, there was consideration that there are atherogenic impacts of infections. In the last century, people abandoned this consideration and the ancient opinion that CHD probably has the infectious etiology has become valid in recent years [3]. The presence of the viral & bacterial pathogens has an association with the inflammatory alterations discovered in atherosclerosis [4, 5]. Research works of past many years have displayed the association between inflammation's markers & atherosclerosis [6].

Current research works have displayed that infections of chronic type due to organisms as *H. pylori*, *Chlamydia pneumonia* and different types of the dental pathogens can be the reason behind the complication of atherosclerosis. If this statement is right, then treatment against these microbes can be helpful for the prevention of coronary artery diseases. A large number of small reports have also tested this phenomenon [2]. Various research studies have displayed a strong association between chronic gastric complication with the *H. pylori* infection & CAD. Some reports concluded that there is a strong association between infections of *H. pylori* with the risk factors of CAD. But the research works about the alterations in the factors of risks for CAD after extermination of *H. pylori* infection are very less and have contradictory outcomes [7]. This research work aimed to examine the association between the seropositivity of *H. pylori* with the availability of the UA, which is one of the controversial problem in this particular subject.

METHODOLOGY:

This was a case-control research work conducted in Allied Hospital Faisalabad from June 2017 to June 2018. In this research study, we evaluated the patients suffering from UA for anti-HP-IgG. There were 96 patients in this research work. The formula for the calculation of the sample size was $N = Z^2P(1-P)/d^2$ in which $N =$ size of sample, $Z =$ CC (Confidence Coefficient 95.0% = 1.960, P is prevalence = 0.50 & d is distance = 0.10. Inclusion standards of the research study includes the patients having more than thirty-five year of age and who were fulfilling the criteria of AHA. We separated the patients into 3 different groups:

- Typical angina pectoris (TAP) present with all three CC,
- Atypical angina pectoris (AAP) present with two CC,
- Non angina pectoris, (NAP) present with only one CC).

The patients with the values of rising in cardiac enzymes, 2-EKG alterations, constant severe angina pain, and doubtful results of anti-HP- IgG, got exclusion from this research study. Every patient filled a well-organized questionnaire including the information about demography traits and other associated variables. We also enrolled 96 age and sex matched controls in this research study. We collected the 5 milliliter clotted blood sample from every patient as well as controls for particular anti-HP-IgG with the utilization of the ELISA method having the sensitivity from 90.0% to 95.0 & specificity from 95.0% to 98.0%. We conducted the commercially present antibody test of IgG for *H. pylori* in accordance with the guidelines of the manufacturer. The analysis of the collected information carried out with the utilization of Chi-square method. The ethical committee of the hospital gave the permission to conduct this research work. We took written consent from every participant to ensure their participation and privacy.

RESULTS:

Total ninety-six patients suffering from UA (Sixty-two TAP, thirty AAP & four NAP) were in the study group with an average age of 56.480 ± 12.91 years (Table: I).

Table I: Study Group Distribution

Type of Angina Pectoris	No	Percent
Typical Angina Pectoris	62	64.58
Atypical Angina Pectoris	30	31.25
Non Angina Pectoris	4	4.17
Total	96	100

There were fifty-five percent females in the study group. There were ninety-six persons in the group of controls with an average age of 58.03±11.53 years. There were fifty-two percent females in the group of controls (Table: II). Total 82.30% (n: 79) patients suffering from UA & 61.10% (n: 55) participants in the group of controls appeared as anti-HP-IgG positive. Exclusion of the 6 participants of the control group carried out because of doubtful results. OR were three with 95.0% confidence interval: from 1.90 to 4.30.

We discovered a strong relation between the positivity of HP-IgG and UA. There was much important disparity in gender and age of the participants of both patient and control group. We also discovered no association between the serum level of HP-IgG and extremity of the medical outcomes of NAP, TAP & AAP in the patients suffering from the complication of unstable angina.

Table II: Sample Composition in Both Groups

Gender	Study Group		Control Group	
	No	Percent	No	Percent
Females	53	55%	50	52%
Males	43	45%	46	48%

DISCUSSION:

This research work elaborated the important association between chronic infections of *H. pylori* & UA. The findings of this research work are in support of the role of *H. pylori* in the promotion of the danger of unstable angina. Adjusted age & sex analysis also discovered no association of positivity of *H. pylori* with the prevalence of the unstable angina. Various research works have stated the relationships between the infections of *H. pylori* & unstable angina [8-11]. This is not obvious whether *H. pylori* infection has actually association with the unstable angina because some of the research works were depending upon biasing, small amount of size of samples etc. The findings of this current research are much consistent with the studies of Rekeinesky and his partners [8, 9], Stone [10] & Fraser [11]. Those works also supported the true association of *H. pylori* with the danger of unstable angina.

Kowalski identified the presence of particular HP-DNA in arteries in the patients suffering from unstable angina [12]. This study also was in support of our findings and there is recommendation of the management of antibiotics against the infection of *H. pylori*. Stone displayed that usage of anti-*H. Pylori* drugs decreased 36.0% the danger of unstable angina in the participants of the study [7]. Various research studies were against the association between *H. pylori* & unstable angina [13, 14]. Semija concluded no relation between these two [13]. Radke was also unable to find the association [14]. This can be due to the difference in the social and economic status of the selected population. Our research work confirmed the findings of previous studies with positive association between *H. pylori* & UA [8-12].

There are some merits of this current research work as patients from both genders were the part of this research work and the average age of the patients of this research work was 56.48±12.91 years that covered a long age span. There are some limitations of this research study as the sample size of this study is very short. It was only cross-sectional research work. We did not examine our patients through histological approach. The controls of this research work were the persons from hospital or the relatives of the patients.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of this research work concluded that there is strong association between infections of *H. pylori* with the presence of UA. The infections of *H. pylori* infections, as diagnosed by sero-positivity of HP-IgG, were available with high danger of UA.

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